

THE IMPORTANCE OF TAXES IN ENSURING INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT

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In our republic, the issues of stimulating innovative activity through taxes have been little studied. It should be noted that the concept of "innovation" was first introduced into the scientific literature in the 30s of the 20th century by the Austrian (and later American) scientist Y. Schumpeter, who emphasized that innovation is an important factor in the development of the economy [1].

In our opinion, only an active entrepreneur who constantly implements innovations, i.e. innovations, inventions, new technologies, techniques, management and labor organization modern systems, will be free from the risk of falling into crisis and bankruptcy. According to P. Drucker, "entrepreneurs are distinguished by innovative thinking. Having innovation is a powerful weapon of entrepreneurship" [2].

"Innovation is a set of innovations, inventions, discoveries, ideas and new approaches in the form of intellectual property, created on the basis of production experience, applied to production, at the same time, bringing economic and social camera" [3]. If an innovative idea is created, applied to production, and proves its economic viability, innovation will not be considered. The created innovations can be called innovations only when they are commercialized, put into practice, and given an economic and social camera.

Innovative entrepreneurship is the process of researching new ideas and introducing existing social and economic relationships into new ones [4]. It can be seen that intellectually great responsibilities and risk are assigned to the subjects of innovative relations in the economy, business environment in the country is of great importance for this responsibilities and risk.

In this regard, the definition given by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev to the concepts of "active entrepreneurship" and "active entrepreneur" is interesting. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Active entrepreneurship is an economic activity that organizes business activity with innovative, i.e., modern approaches, advanced technology and

management tools. By an active entrepreneur, we mean businessmen who are able to produce competitive products, and most importantly, create new jobs, feed not only themselves and their families, but also benefit the entire society" [5] he emphasized.

The enterprise organizes innovative activities that rationally use the existing business environment, the enterprise develops its future strategy based on the strategic possibilities of the business environment, and the enterprise receives additional benefits in exchange for the realization of its economic-intellectual ideas. The dependence of business environment factors on innovative entrepreneurship is presented in the following table.

As can be seen from Figure 1, the business environment in the country lacks important economic mechanisms that create innovative activities.

Based on the above-mentioned circumstances, the business environment for innovative entrepreneurship in the country:

- introduction of innovative processes in the enterprise and use of existing resources;
- conclusion of contracts with internal and external partners regarding implementation of innovative ideas and production of modern products in the enterprise;
- provides a number of opportunities, such as finding financial partners and using the funds of venture funds for the implementation of innovative ideas and the production of modern products.\

The concept of forming a national innovation system began to develop in the early 1980s of the last century. In this case, the word "national" means exactly the meaning of the "state" innovation system. [6].

In our opinion, the tax policy conducted in the country is one of the main economic levers that directly affects not only the innovative development, but also the socio-economic development of the society. Current tax rates and tax burden in the national economy are important factors that quickly affect the activities of national producers, entrepreneurs and foreign investors. If the tax rates in the economy are low, and the tax burden is being gradually reduced, in such conditions, a wide path will be opened for entrepreneurship, the material interests of producers of goods and services will increase, and these factors will create conditions for economic activity and rapid development in the country.

In our country's rational macroeconomic policy and taxation, which is its most influential and important direction, priority is given to the interests of producers of goods and services and business entities. If we analyze the positive changes in tax rates in recent years, we pay attention to the following (Table 1).

Table 1

Changes in tax payment rates in Uzbekistan from 1992 to 2021

Tax types	Top tax rates from 1992-2009	Rates set in 2010	Rates set in 2021	Decline
Value added tax	30 percent	20 percent	15 percent	2 equal to
Юридик шахсларнинг даромад (фойда) солиғи	45 percent	9 percent	15 percent	3 equal to
Юридик шахслар учун мулк солиғи	5 percent	3,5 percent	2 percent	2,5 equal to
Single tax payment for small businesses	15,2 percent	7,0 percent	4 percent	3,8 equal to
Income tax of individuals	60 up to percent	22 up to percent	12 percent	5 equal to
Single social payment	40 percent	25 percent	12 percent	3,3 equal to

The table shows that in order to encourage the expansion of consumer demand and production of goods (works, services) in the periods taken for analysis, the value added tax rate was reduced from 30 percent to 15 percent and reduced by 2 times. The small business and private enterprise single tax payment rate was reduced from 5% to 3.5% of gross income from 15.2% in 2005, to 4% in 2021 and reduced to 3.8 times. In the years of independence, the reduction of the income tax rate of legal entities will positively serve to replenish the working capital of enterprises and organizations, and to strengthen the material and technical base.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the reduction of the rate of a certain type of tax is of special socio-economic importance. For example, a single social payment, a reduction in personal income tax rates will have a positive effect on the continuous increase in the incomes of working people and the population, and will serve to provide them with stronger social protection. As a result of such an effective tax policy, the funds that must be paid at the disposal of economic entities are a clear manifestation of the care and support shown to them by the state.

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